

WHAT IS A CASE STUDY?

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Annotation: This of case technologies in the article basis of the “Case study” method appear to be, how in places application and how importance occupation reach about word goes.

Key words: Harvard, case study, Socrates, casebook, law, business, economics, problematic situation, teaching method.

Each society and time to himself okay pedagogical views to the system have will be Why? certain time and in space living of people education - upbringing about leader thoughts, ideals his in pedagogy reflection reached will be. (Yo‘ldoshev Q. Tashkent 2023, p.25.) Today in the day study in the activity teacher and student cooperation provision, education of recipients independent knowledge take and his opinion free statement do it to get development education in front standing important from duty one is considered

People lifetime during or the work activity during different different to problems, situations face will come. Problematic to the situation solution give get, right road choose to know that's it activity of the owner knowledge, skills depend. Problematic situations the situation learner and to him practical solution “case study” in the future to the body coming problematic of situations the solution teacher, new solutions work to exit referrer technology is considered Case technology main purpose study group of students knowledge get process activation. Case study technology the subject independent learning, problem essence determine, own the point look protection make sense conclusion output, data comparison, generalization and analysis to do competencies formation service to do with separate stands. In this students activity problems solution to do ways difficult to find to situations concerned all to thoughts own their views free statement to do will be directed. (Kambarova S. Tashkent. 2016. - p. 16.)

Case study method about more precisely to know for his formation history not to learn possible no. Case study first times Harvard of the university right in the school in 1870 by Ch. C. Langdell applied was (<https://casestudies.law.harvard.edu>) Term right from the field come in that he has arrived account take approachable if so, in the past difficult decisions are complicated to situations face came man situation learning through decision acceptance done. For example, crime exposed to do for, crime happen done condition there is details with studied. And this right in their schools study method being service did. For example, *15 years old Murad named student a classmate Said's to the person touching words with insulted, dispute during Said's glasses broke his phone strength with pulling took. Said tomorrow day phone when asked Murad phone did not admit that he had received it. Said to the court appeal did.* This case teacher to the students present does Students the situation by learning come out and legal basically solution they try to find. Case method to students complicated the problem quickly

understand quickly reasonable solution to find and this the solution to others short and efficient way deliver ability will give. Students interest woke up case method professional to issues interest strengthens.

Case method Harvard legal by Christopher Columbus Langdell at his school before pushed Socrates to the principles (*Socrates himself reflection carry on and beliefs, assumptions critical check favors. People their own purpose and strategies regularly respectively question so, own on performance*) based teaching method casebook (*practical the work style similar to, US law in their schools main teaching method is legal of the rules very abstract conclusions from learning according to practical affairs with engage*) from the method developed. Casebook method like the case method students difficult to the problem face came real person role to get calls.

Harvard in 1920 business school (HBS) teachers of lawyers teaching to the experience relying on economic in practice sure situations analysis reach and discussion to do of education main method reached from their choice after this teaching style wide app Ethyl started Various situational exercises. The first book collected in 1921 Copeland and Harvard business of the school leader Wallace Donam published under the auspices of. Case technology in development Harvard and Manchester schools separately important have, they from each other use methods through difference does. Case study method the first times social 1929 family by Frederic le Play in science budget statistics in the calculation used. Further case studies social in the sciences new theories in creating by sociologists Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss in 1967, "based on in theory" study method as used. XX of the work in their heads Harvard of the school teachers in their classes lecture reading in the process to thinking exclamation point issues complete those who did not explain it to tables the answers of students themselves who tried to find and of students stated solutions note by doing those who went. This is the process during different character students including problems solutions to find encouraged. 70-80 years of XX century come this technology the world across wide spread. Case study technology of the second 1990s at half Russian specialists by second there is learn started. Economy in the field take going wide on the scale reforms as a result, it is necessary at the time independent and right the decision acceptance it is difficult one from the situation emitting, right risk do it who knows. Economists are in high demand increased. Of this as a result a lot higher education in institutions being taught case technology in sciences apply began, as well as the economy to the field new directions added: management, marketing, sociology, political science and others. This directions through education to the field interactive teaching styles come in came. (F. T. Rabbimova. Pedagogists. 2022) Now exactly in the style of the case teachable study There are many universities: Harvard business school, IESE business School, Columbia business school, Singapore management University, Blavatnik the government school, INCAE business School of Business, Hyderabad ICFAI School of Business, Acton School, Amsterdam Hogeschool, Asia Institute of Management, India management institute, Richard Ivey business School, Harvard John F. Kennedy University of Government School of Commerce, Nagoya and business university NUCB business under School, Virginia of business at Darden University School, Columbia journalism school, Mailman community health School, Columbia university.

Case style relied on of centers purpose teachers and students in the middle this in the field knowledge, skill and experience exchange through the case style promote is to do Case methodology according to seminars transfer, scholarships offer do, magazine publication

reach and global work method awards organize to do such as different activity with are engaged.

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